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Reading Kamila Shamsie's *Home Fire* in the Indian Classroom

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Abstract:

Kamila Shamsie's *Home Fire*, a novelistic adaptation of Sophocles's *Antigone*, examines a complex relationship between identity and citizenship. The novel exposes the precarity of British Muslims in the post 9/11 West, as anti-immigrant and Islamophobic politics become increasingly strident. This essay argues that studying *Home Fire* in an Indian literature classroom can generate critical discussions about politics, identity, colonialism, and citizenship, opening up difficult socio-political questions in our own context. A novel about British Muslim lives resonates with the Indian reader because of its complex exploration of a minority community in a majoritarian society, and the clamorous political assertions of exclusion in recent times. By inviting postcolonial readings of classical literature, the novel encourages innovative pedagogical approaches and reading practices. The paper further emphasises the potential of the study of literature to critically interrogate received ideologies and discursive frameworks, enabling the possibility of ethical political intervention.

Keywords: Citizenship, Islamophobia, Pedagogy, Literary Reading.

As the crisis in the Middle East rages and gathers in its swoop the entire globe, it is instructive to read Shamsie's *Home Fire*, a novelistic adaptation of Sophocles's *Antigone*,

published in 2017. Set against the context of the rise of ISIS (The Islamic State) in Syria and Iraq, a wider escalation of 'War on Terror', Kamila Shamie's *Home Fire* tells the story of two British Muslim families who find themselves on two sides of the political divide.

Led by America and backed by dominant European countries, the state of Israel's actions in Gaza, widely condemned as the genocide of Palestinians, continues to be defended and vindicated. While Western governments deploy a pernicious rhetoric and uphold "Israel's right to self-defence" and continue the supply of arms to Israel, the world watches the relentless annihilation of Gaza - its hospitals, schools, universities, homes, institutions, and thousands of women and children. Enraged and refusing to be complicit in this inhuman project, students on US campuses called out their University administrations and demanded divestment of universities from the weapons industry. Predictably, the protesting students and faculty were met with the most brutal police repression, expulsions, suspensions, and administrative imperiousness. The university spaces quickly turned into security zones with armed police forcefully dismantling student encampments. The protesters organised sit-ins, demonstrations, study sessions, open classrooms - the whole pedagogic structure evoked an ideal space of learning. These protests spread across the US, Europe, and the UK, in the most elite campuses, which have historically claimed to be liberal, inclusive, and democratic spaces. The blatant disjunction between these claims and the systematic and uniformly undemocratic, racist, and heavy-handed suppression of dissent forces a reassessment of the function of the University and the relationship between pedagogy and politics, education and political practice.

Universities with their institutionalised legitimacy, despite their claims to intellectual autonomy, are not necessarily radical spaces. The set protocols of curricula, methodological procedures, and support from states or private funding ensure that, more often than not, the established social, racial, caste, and gender hierarchies are not seriously disturbed. In the last decade in the Indian public education system, even the veneer of intellectual autonomy and

dissident thinking has rapidly eroded. Reading and pedagogical practices are now more rigorously controlled and surveilled, and the challenges to the dominant state discourse – ideological, political, or national - can lead to retributive treatment or, in some cases, long incarceration.

In the late 80s, the colonial provenance of English Studies was incisively interrogated, and the ‘tainted’ history of the discipline became the subject of much critical reevaluation with a determined attempt to “decolonise” the curriculum. This led to thinking about pedagogical exercises in the classroom while teaching the English canon, which was predominantly White, Male, and Western, alongside diversifying the curriculum to include texts from Indian languages in translation and other postcolonial writing. This inclusive approach was meant to challenge the established protocols of literary readings, canon-formation, and reshape the discipline to reflect India’s postcolonial situation. However, as Priyamvada Gopal avers,

“An intellectually expansive curriculum that, taken as a whole, puts different ideas, texts and traditions in conversation is pedagogically sound. ‘Diversity’ in and of itself, however, is not the same as ‘decolonisation’ and can serve to militate against it if all it generates is a glib pluralism that allows the centre, and its attendant orthodoxies, to remain unchallenged and unchanged” (Gopal, 2021).

According to Bhambra – “ ‘decolonising’ remains a contested term, consisting of a heterogeneity of viewpoints, approaches, political projects and normative concerns” (Bhambra, G.K., 2018, 2). In the Western academy, Bhambra observes,

anti-racist and anticolonial struggles were articulated in, though, and against Western universities. Campus mobilisations, the formation of student societies, and the publication of student papers knitted higher education and anti-colonialism into a rich

tapestry of radical activism in the colonial metropole. Taken together, such histories of anti-racist struggle have always included concerns for research and education. . . (3).

India has a rich history of students' solidarity movements that have, at crucial political junctures, aligned themselves with social justice projects, resisted authoritarian measures such as the Emergency, and, more recently, opposed controversial citizenship laws. The decolonising project, in the current political climate in India, cannot be restricted to mere diversity of textual representation in the curriculum, but should ask key political questions about structural inequities of gender, caste, and communities, and be vigilant of the appropriation of the idea of 'decolonisation' by political discourses that peddle a false, ahistorical, monocultural, and mythical precolonial past.

Reading a text like *Home Fire* in a literature classroom can produce a range of energies that can enable us to think about politics, identities, colonialism, and citizenship in complex ways, opening up difficult socio-political questions in our own context. *Home Fire* exposes the precarity of British Muslims in the post 9/11 West as anti-immigrant and Islamophobic politics become more clamorous, threatening to render citizens stateless. The 'War on Terror' legitimises the intrusive and invasive surveillance of racialised Muslims. At the heart of this rhetoric is the consolidation of an exclusivist, racist, nationalist framing of citizenship rights. While the demonisation of the Muslim body and identity has become political commonsense since 9/11, *Home Fire*, by pitting two British Muslim families, the Pashas and Lones, against each other, exposes the ideological basis of racist politics. As a novelistic adaptation of Sophocles' *Antigone*, *Home Fire* investigates the ideological racism perpetrated by the 'War of Terror' by collapsing the boundaries between family, nation, and law.

In the novel, Isma is the eldest of three siblings, who took over the caregiving of the family after the death of their mother and grandmother, and a father who was a fleeting

presence in the family. Adil Pasha had been a terrorist who fought in Kashmir, Kosovo, Afghanistan, and Chechnya, and died of a seizure before he was put on a plane to be transferred to Guantanamo Bay. The tragic abandonment of the father and the disgrace surrounding his death and disappearance influence Parvaiz to join the media wing of ISIS in Syria. Isma, after a long hiatus, goes to Amherst to pursue her PhD on “The Sociological Impact of the War on Terror”.

The crisis in the novel is precipitated when Parvaiz, disillusioned by ISIS, attempts to return to Britain but is brutally killed by unknown assailants. Aneeka, Parvaiz’s twin, is determined to bring her dead brother home. The Home Secretary of Britain, Karamat Lone, a British Muslim politician, forbids the return of the dead. Aneeka launches a public attack on Karamat and the British government’s decision to revoke Parvaiz and her citizenship, exerting her political and filial right to bring her dead brother back to Britain and give him a proper burial. As an adaptation of Sophocles’ *Antigone*, the novel, according to Peter Ho Davies, is a “shrewdly subversive move to tell this immigrant story via a tale so central to the Western canon” (Ho Davies, 2017, 14).

As the Home Secretary in the Tory government in the UK, Theresa May introduced a policy revoking the citizenship of naturalised terror suspects, especially those who held dual nationality. In retrospect, this policy was a prequel to Brexit that evoked racist and anti-immigrant sentiments to affect Britain’s exit from the European Union. Stripping the citizenship of twenty Britons of alleged “jihadis” in Syria in 2013, the Home Office said: “Citizenship is a privilege, not a right, and the home secretary will remove British citizenship from individuals where she feels it is conducive to the public good to do so” (Association, 2013).

In Kamila Shamsie’s *Home Fire*, these words are chillingly attributed to Karamat Lone, who, after taking office as Home Secretary, offered his unconditional gratitude to Britain. In

2018, a year after *Home Fire* was published, Sadiq Javed succeeded May as the Home Secretary. Evoking section 40 of the British Nationality Act of 1981, Javid revoked the citizenship of Shamina Begum, a British-born national, who travelled to Syria as a young girl to join ISIS. Begum was born in 1999 in East London to parents of Bangladeshi descent. Her British citizenship was revoked on grounds of national security soon after she was found nine months pregnant in a Syrian refugee camp in February 2019. Home Secretary Sajid Javid argued in favour of preventing anyone who joined ISIS from returning and said Begum was a threat to national security. In the novel, Karamat, modelled on Creon in Sophocles' *Antigone*, alludes to the Nationality, Immigration and Asylum Act of 2002, whereby the British government can strip any dual-national Briton, whether naturalised or British-born, of their citizenship status. Near the end of *Home Fire*, we learn that Karamat is planning to expand the law similarly: 'It was, clearly, the sensible fulfilment of a law that was so far only half made' (214). Karamat revokes the citizenship of Parvaiz (Polyneices) and Aneeka (Antigone). Shamsie presciently predicted Sajid Javid's political stance and fictionally anticipated the citizen-stripping case of Shamina Begum.

Rehana Ahmed in *Writing British Muslims: Religion, Class and Multiculturalism* discusses South Asian Muslims in Britain and their negotiations of the British state's liberal multicultural rhetoric. She argues convincingly against the boundary between the public and the private, observing that the public sphere can never be non-aligned. Western liberalism's attempts to consign Muslim practices to the private sphere marginalise religious minorities and reinforce a set of dominant values. The title and the plot of *Home Fire* evoke the metaphor of Home (both as the domestic sphere and the State), and present the contentious issues of citizenship, justice, and law through familial and filial relationships. Following a long tradition of political adaptations of *Antigone*, Shamsie interrogates the controversial anti-immigration, Islamophobic politics of post 9/11 Britain.

The epigraph of the novel - “The ones we love...are the enemies of the state” is a quote from Seamus Heaney’s “Burial at Thebes”, a version of *Antigone* published in 2004. Heaney’s adaptation was a reflection on the Irish/ British conflict and the Bush administration’s ‘War on Terror’. Shamsie acknowledges her debt to Anne Carson’s *Antigone* (2015), Ali Smith’s *The Story of Antigone* (2013), and Gillian Slovo’s verbatim play *Another World: How We Lost Our Children to Islamic State* (2016), which was commissioned shortly after Shamsie started working on *Home Fire*. According to Naomi Weiss,

Antigone, more than any other surviving ancient Greek tragedy, has a rich history of adaptations and remakings that force upon their audiences urgent sociopolitical issues and questions . . . Such plays and productions have often used Sophocles’ tragedy to explore ways for the oppressed and powerless to publicly counter their powerful oppressors. *Home Fire*, as a novel focused on Muslim identity, Islamophobia, and citizenship rights in contemporary Britain, fits within this long tradition of politically resonant Antigones (Weiss, 2021, 4).

In his investigation of contemporary American war writing and the pervasive evocation of the Greek epics Iliad and Odyssey, Peter Krauss argues that the epics ascribe heroic stature to the valour and honour of men at war. “Preoccupation with Homeric heroism privileges the soldiers’ quest for ‘personal redemption’ and ‘recovery’ at the expense of considering the lives of those they harm” (Krauss, 2020, 14). “More recently, American writing about the post-9/11 wars continues to overtly reference the classics, especially the Homeric epics that lionize the solitary, heroic, male warrior” (16). By adapting the Sophoclean tragedy, rather than the Homeric epic, Krauss argues, “Shamsie engages with the vital project—at once feminist, anti-imperialist, and anti-Islamophobic— of wresting victimhood from the invader and reframing the war as a needlessly violent fiasco” (15). Moving away from male-centric war epics,

Shamsie shifts focus to the women who struggle against the omnipresent state machinery of bureaucratized counter-terrorism surveillance and racial profiling of Muslims.

While Isma quietly subverts and negotiates being a Muslim woman and the daughter and sister to radicalised jihadi fighters, Aneeka launches a public challenge to the legitimacy of the law that strips her brother and her of their citizenship. She poses the question of Justice to delegitimise the discourse of legality.

As Krauss's study of adaptations of Greek heroic epics in contemporary American war writing indicates, the study of classics and their modern adaptations can create the possibility of political readings of the classical canon in ways that reflect and contend with contemporary issues outside the classroom. Antigone's narrative serves as a lens through which Shamsie examines the complex and contested terrain of political assertions regarding British Muslim identity, particularly the identity of Muslim women. This exploration can facilitate critical discussions on and a framework for interrogating competing claims and counterclaims surrounding Muslim identity in India, along with an investigation of the lingering effects of the Partition on the subcontinent. With the rise of majoritarianism in India, the idea of the 'Muslim' has become central to political discussions. More recently, the controversial Citizenship Amendment Bill, proposed in 2019, sparked nationwide protests spear-headed by the old Muslim women of Shaheen Bagh and gathered overwhelming support from large groups, including university students. University administrations followed the Centre's line and disallowed any agitation within the campuses.

The eruption of community and majoritarian identity-based politics that betray the principles of equality and universal rights of all citizens, irrespective of class, caste, gender, faith or community cannot be elided in classroom discussions, and a text like *Home Fire* lends itself to complex discussions on these urgent political developments. The complex treatment

of Muslim identity in *Home Fire* provokes us to investigate contemporary discourses and political framing of minorities in India.

In the opening chapter of the novel, when Isma is at the airport to travel to Amherst in the USA, she is interrogated to prove her “Britishness”. She has already rehearsed this trial with her sister Aneeka, who ventriloquizes the voice of the state--- the tropes of interrogation that presume guilt of a Muslim, till she is proven, only tentatively, innocent. In what appears to be a farcical set of questions - from Shias, to suicide bombers, to Iraq, to dating sites, the Queen, democracy, etc - the novel demonstrates the Islamophobic and anti-immigrant discourse of the Security State. As the questioning continues, Isma recollects her practice session with Aneeka. In the role-playing session, Aneeka had chided her sister for being too compliant. Aneeka, Isma had thought, “with her law-student brain, who knew everything about her rights and nothing about the fragility of her place in the world” (Shamsie, 2016, 6).

The novel builds on this initial scene to demonstrate what Islamophobia does, and exposes the operational technologies that mount and consequently manufacture Muslim immigrant subjectivities. The characters of Isma and Aneeka adopt different positions in their resistance to the state. Structured in five parts, each corresponding to Isma, Eamonn, Pervaiz, Aneeka, and Karamat - following the 5 act structure of Sophocles’s *Antigone*, the novel explores the characters’ political motivations, subjectivities, and conflicts. Within the framework of a domestic novel, the work explodes the public/private dyad, as personal relationships are shown to be violently inflected and shattered by the state, which, ironically, is represented by Karamat, a British Muslim, much like Creon in the Greek tragedy.

The novel opens with Isma in Massachusetts, who goes to do her PhD after a long hiatus, under a Kashmiri supervisor, Dr Hira Shah. Isma, as part of her academic work, chooses to co-author a paper with her supervisor entitled ‘The Insecurity State: Britain and the Instrumentalisation of Fear’. The intrusive and expansive technologies of surveillance are

legitimised on the presumption of perpetual threat from “enemies” within. In the novel, Isma’s thesis turns this presupposition on its head by drawing attention not to the precarity of possible victims but to the alleged perpetrators of this threat. Isma had heard Dr Hira Shah’s lecture, where she discussed counter-terrorism laws and the UK’s “Prevention of Terrorism Act, 2005”, enacted after the 9/11 attacks. Isma, who was present at the lecture, had interjected and argued that there is a long tradition in British Imperialism that deprived people of their rights and liberties. The only difference in contemporary times, she asserted, was that now it is being deployed against British citizens. Isma’s academic project is a study of the “sociological impact of the War on Terror” that examines the precautionary measures taken by the state aimed at British Muslims. This contention brings to the fore the discussions on citizenship and the racism inherent in the idea of Britishness.

The issue of Muslim identity concerning the hijab, interestingly, is brought up by Eamonn, whose name, Isma knows, was an Anglicised version of Ayman, to indicate Karamat Lone’s assimilation with the White majority. Eamonn, unbeknownst to his lineage, tells Isma – “it must be difficult to be a Muslim in the world today” (21). Shamsie’s novel reveals the ideology of Whiteness and White privilege through Muslim characters, thus complicating an easy binary between the ‘self’ and ‘other’, and the stereotypical representation of Muslim identity and politics as homogeneous. Isma and Aneeka’s decision to wear the hijab provokes a complex reading of Muslim female agency within a hostile, racist public sphere, and the careful negotiation between gendered cultural practices of the community while challenging orthodox, patriarchal community practices.

The crack in the relationship between Isma and Aneeka occurs when it is discovered that Isma had informed the police about Parvaiz’s induction into ISIS. Aneeka lashes out at her sister for this betrayal and making it impossible for their brother to come home. Isma says, “We’re in no position to let the state question our loyalties...I wasn’t going to let him make

you suffer for the choices he'd made" (Shamsie, 2016, 42). Isma's subversive resistance to counter-terrorism is reflected in her academic work, yet she perceptively approaches the effects of openly defying the state with a sense of personal and political pragmatism.

Aneeka, like Antigone, openly challenges the state, and her defiance becomes an international public event. In an interesting improvisation, unlike Antigone and Creon, Aneeka never comes face to face with Karamat. Aneeka, in defiance of the law, travels to Pakistan to bring her brother's body back to Britain where he can get a rightful burial. While the earlier sections of the novel explore the internal conflicts of characters, the latter half of the novel is exaggeratedly public and performative. Aneeka's motives and actions come to us mediated through a polyphony of voices - through media reports, Karamat's reactions, Eamonn's internal conflicts and rebellion. Aneeka's extreme act of challenge to the State is theatrically enacted when she sits vigil over her brother's corpse in absolute public view in park outside the British Embassy in Karachi. Her rebellion is aesthetically displayed as she sits with a melting ice coffin with her brother's body wrapped in white sheet, rose petals and leaves flying in the wind - in full view of television cameras, watched by bystanders, and telecast internationally. The battle of ideologies and political perspectives are articulated not only by Aneeka and Karamat but the whole media machinery- through interviews (Karamat), television coverage of Aneeka in Karachi, misogynistic and racist op-eds, and the liberal press voicing a counter-narrative. Like the chorus in the Greek play, the media circus represents the wider political communities and their irreconcilable differences on anti-immigration policies, Islamophobia, and citizenship rights. According to Weiss, "Shamsie urges her readers to play a part, to enter a performance, in relation to the story but also to the actual policies, practices, and communities to which it refers..." (18) The novel implicates the reader in the narrative through this spectatorial trope by evoking our own mediated response and assumptions about narratives of 'War on Terror'.

In her discussion of the ethics of reading of *Home Fire*, Rutkowska argues that the media coverage of Parvaiz's death, which is ridden by misinformation, partisanship, and distortion, emphasizes the "the repercussions of inattentiveness to language in the world outside the novel, as well as showing the reader how the media coverage of the Begum case had an effect on how the British public responded to it" (14). An ethical reading of the novel demands a close attention to language, tropes, stereotypes, and ideological positionalities that manufacture the discourse of racist and communitarian polarisation.

The interplay between the characters in the novel represents a spectrum of positions on Muslim identity in Britain. The novel precludes a convenient dichotomy between races and communities as the central characters are all from the Muslim community. The majoritarian prejudices are articulated through the choric voice of the traditional and new media that produce and replay endlessly the broad public consensus on a racialised and homogenised perception of Muslim identity. Through the character of Karamat, Shamsie reveals that racial and community identities are historical rather than essentialised. By adapting the theatrical choric trope in the novel form, Shamsie lays bare the architecture of the media and surveillance apparatus and the role they play in contemporary times in controlling and manipulating public opinion through spectacularity and repetition. By juxtaposing the more introspective aspects of the characters' motives and challenges with the spectacularity of the media representations, the novel forces the reader to critically evaluate their own political and identitarian assumptions.

A novel about British Muslim lives resonates with the Indian classroom because of its complex exploration of a minority community in a majoritarian society, and the strident political assertions of exclusion in recent times. The mainstream media in India has gradually capitulated to political pressure and is now a chief instrument in fuelling religious polarisation by platforming the state's ideological interests. The hydra-headed spread of information

technologies is instrumentalised to manipulate mass public opinion on minorities and promote majoritarian myths. *Home Fire* exposes the discursive patterns and the theatrical toolkit used by the media by evoking a critical understanding of these processes. Read by students of literature, language, and communications, the novel can invite insightful discussions on the role of the media in contemporary India. Shamsie's adaptation of a Greek play to articulate the concerns of British Muslims in the context of civilisational polarisation in the West and the associated political ramifications for immigrants, minorities, and people of colour enables a creative reading of classics, beyond the standard critical orthodoxy on the canon. The novel prompts us to engage with Classical literature as postcolonial readers and opens up the possibility for pedagogically innovative reading practices.

The classroom is a potent space for debate, discussion, and evaluation of received ideologies and discursive structures, enabling critical readings of politics and culture. As universities become more diverse demographically, social, cultural, and political conflicts and contests play out within campuses. The classroom becomes a negotiated social space that often produces unease, but through that unease, rather than its elision, emerges the possibility of critical solidarities and democratic politics. The pedagogical exercise is to work out a model of consensus-building through disagreements, mutuality, and plurality of perspectives both within the classroom and outside.

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